

ABSORPTION AND FLUORESCENCE SPECTRA OF CHROMONES

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Absorption and fluorescence spectra of 7-hydroxy-2-methyl-, 7-hydroxy-2-methyl-3-acetyl-, 7-acetoxy-2-methyl-, 7-methoxy-2-methyl-, 5-hydroxy-2-methyl-chromones have been studied. Absorption spectrum of chromone is modified by introduction of hydroxyls, which make additional resonance possible (e.g. 5-OH; 7-OH derivatives). Etherification of 7-OH does not change the nature of absorption. Acetylation reverts the spectrum to that of chromone without any hydroxyl. Fluorescence is exhibited only by 7-hydroxychromone. Chelation (5-OH deriv.) results in complete inhibition of fluorescence.

Absorption spectra of γ -pyrone and chromone have been reported by Gibbs *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 4895). The former exhibits a maximum at $40.7 \times 10^3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (250m μ region) with fine structure on low-frequency side, viz., at $39.3 \times 10^3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $38.4 \times 10^3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Chromone has been shown to have two bands, one resolved into two adjacent bands of the same ϵ at $33.2 \times 10^3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $33.8 \times 10^3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (301, 296m μ) and another at $42.2 \times 10^3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (237m μ), with ϵ values of 7.9×10^3 and 10.5×10^3 respectively.

According to Aronoff (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1940, 5, 561) γ -pyrone has another band in 200 m μ region. Chromone, he reports, exhibits in addition to the two γ -pyrone maxima, viz. 200 and 250 m μ , a third at 300 m μ . Mentzer and Meunier (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1944, 11, 302) have reported the spectra in EtOH of 3-methylchromone and 3-ethyl-6-methyl derivative. Other absorption spectra data for various chromone derivatives have been reported by organic chemists (Schmutz, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1951, 34, 767; Bolleter, *ibid.*, 1951, 34, 186).

Berson's qualitative interpretation (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 3521) of the absorption of pyrones and benzopyrones includes the following resonance structures for γ -pyrone :

According to Berson, the Kekule heteropolar structures, A₂ and A₃, make significant contribution in the first excited state. Inclusion of 'intermediate' dipolar structures is important because the probability of direct transition from structure A₁ to the extreme heteropolar structures A₂, A₃ is very small. Only small contribution is made by dipolar structures in the ground state of chromone (cf. LeFevre, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 196).

There are no quantitative measurements on fluorescence spectra of chromones, reported so far. Seshadri *et al.* (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1940, 12A, 375; 1951, 34A, 319)

have qualitatively studied the fluorescence of chromone derivatives in the light of chemical constitution. Their work consists in visual examination of fluorescence excited by daylight. In their discussions no regard has been taken of the exciting radiation. The concentration range at which the observations have been made are not reported. Due to concentration quenching, erroneous observations could have easily been made.

These authors have studied the effect of acid, alkali and various substitutions on the fluorescence of chromone nucleus. The data are represented graphically in Figs. 1-4.

Absorption

The characteristic chromone spectrum (two bands at 2,500 and 3,000Å) is modified by introduction of hydroxyl groups, their methyl ethers and other substituents, and this is found to be due to the possibility of additional resonances over and above that in the chromone structure. The presence of a 2-Me group in the hydroxychromones, studied here, can reasonably be assumed to have little effect on absorption excepting a very minor hyperconjugative effect of -CH₃.

7-OH group in 2-methylchromone modifies the chromone spectrum radically, giving rise to absorption bands at 216, 248 (fine structure), and 294 mμ with extinction coefficients of 20800, 19,550 and 11,900 respectively.

The additional resonance possible with this group is similar to that suggested by Aronoff for 7-hydroxyflavone (*loc. cit.*):

Considering the normal resonance, the higher dipole strength of transition, as compared to that of the corresponding α -pyrones (coumarins), gives rise to comparatively high integrated absorption. $\int \epsilon d\nu$ for 4-methyl-7-hydroxycoumarin and 2-methyl-7-hydroxychromone in neutral solution is 36.2 and 52.4 respectively. The oscillator strength of the longest-wave band (294 mμ) of the latter is also higher, viz., 0.28, as compared to 0.23 for the corresponding α -pyrone derivative. In alkaline ($10^{-4}N$) medium, where ionisation of the hydroxyl is increased, an additional band, removed to the red, is produced at 338 mμ ($\epsilon=5,180$). This can be attributed to the resonance of the type:

in the ionic state. A 5-OH group in 2-methylchromone also influences the absorption spectrum, due to the possibility of the additional resonance of the type:

Now the absorption bands lie at 325, 252, 233 and 226.5 $m\mu$ with $\epsilon=4,730$; 13,550; 20,750 and 20,500 respectively. The oscillator strengths of the bands at 325 and 252 $m\mu$ are 0.09 and 0.21 respectively.

There is, however, no change in spectrum with p_H . This can be attributed to the inhibition of the ionisation of the hydroxyl at 5-position, because of strong chelation, as already reported by Simpson and Garden (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 4638) from chromatographic study.

The methylation of the hydroxyl at 7-position retains the nature of absorption spectrum completely, because even now the additional resonance, as with 7-OH, is possible. There being no ionisation now, the p_H -dependence of the spectra as well as the additional long-wave band characteristic of the ionic form is absent. Methylation shifts the absorption slightly to shorter wave-length but increases ϵ and $f\epsilon dv$. The oscillator strength of the longest-wave band of 7-methoxy-2-methylchromone (292 $m\mu$) is 0.30 as compared to 0.28 of the 294 $m\mu$ band of the 7-OH analogue.

Acetylation of the hydroxyl at 7-position reverts the spectrum to that of chromone. This is obviously due to the fact that the additional resonance possible with -OH is inhibited by its conversion into -O.CO.CH₃.

Introduction of a 3-acetyl group in 7-hydroxy-2-methylchromone, though retains the spectral character of absorption in the longest-wave band yet there is a radical change in the spectrum in the shorter wave-length side. The bands now lie at 295 and 249 $m\mu$ with minima at 275 and 220 $m\mu$. With this acetyl group the additional resonance due to -OH is not affected; however, the normal resonance in chromone nucleus is affected. The 'additional' resonance, which is more important in hydroxy compounds, being unaffected, we observe that the introduction of acetyl group at 3-position does not produce such a radical change in the absorption of the corresponding -OH compound, as when the acetyl group is at a position *ortho* to the hydroxyl (e.g., 8-acetylbelleferone, work under publication).

The dependence of spectrum of 3-acetyl-2-methyl-7-hydroxychromone on p_H and exhibition of isobestic points is, of course, expected. The integrated absorption of this compound is slightly greater than that of 2-methyl-7-hydroxychromone: $\int \epsilon dv = 53.7$ and 52.4 respectively, for neutral solutions.

Fluorescence

Amongst the few chromones available for this study, 7-hydroxy-2-methylchromone only exhibited a fluorescence emission comparable in intensity with the corresponding α -pyrones. The other derivatives had very low fluorescence, so as not to enable the authors to determine the fluorescence spectrum, though the approximate values of F_{max} were determined in each case. 7-Hydroxy-2-methylchromone shows blue fluorescence

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

FIG. 4

FIG. 3

with maxima at 470, 470 and 485 $m\mu$ for $10^{-4}N$ alkaline, neutral, and $10^{-4}N$ acidic solutions respectively. The total fluorescence, $\int F d\nu$, in these media is 10,250, 6,050 and 1,350 respectively as compared to values of 13,500, 10,500 and 8,400 respectively, for 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (work under publication). The increase in resonance on introduction of 7-OH should be responsible for its fluorescing property. As found in coumarins, the ionic form of 7-hydroxy-2-methylchromone has also much greater quantum efficiency, and the fluorescence band for ionic form lies at shorter wave-length than that of the molecular form, notwithstanding the fact that the ionic form has an additional absorption band, much removed to longer wave-length.

Although resonance is increased with an introduction of 5-OH in 2-methylchromone, the inhibition of fluorescence is most probably due to strong chelation of this hydroxyl with the carbonyl of the γ -pyrone. However, there are exceptions to this generalisation of inhibition of fluorescence by chelation, e.g. quinizarin (Bowen and Wokes, "Fluorescence of Solutions", Longmans, 1953).

Acetylation of the hydroxyl at 7-position renders this group ineffective to produce the additional resonance and the behaviour is more or less the same as that of chromone without -OH substituent; hence no fluorescence.

The etherification of the hydroxyl at 7-position inhibits the fluorescence, F_{max} being now ~ 5 as compared to 2,510 for 7-hydroxy-2-methylchromone in neutral solution. Introduction of 3-acetyl group in 7-hydroxy-2-methylchromone also results in a great set-back in quantum efficiency. The values of F_{max} now, are 25, 10 and ~ 0 for alkaline, neutral and acidic solutions respectively, as compared to 3,925, 2,510 and 565 respectively when there is no acetyl group. The chromone resonance being affected by this group, the normal electron drift from the anionoid oxygen at 1 to cationoid oxygen at 4 is hampered by the presence of the carbonyl group at 3-position.

EXPERIMENTAL

Absorption measurements were made with a Beckman DU spectrophotometer and the fluorescence spectra obtained with a fluorimeter assembly consisting of a hydrogen discharge (source), a Fuess constant-deviation spectroscopy as the dispersing element, and an IP28 photoelectron-multiplier tube at the exit slit, with an additional amplifier (cf. Jatkar and Mattoo, *J. Univ. Poona*, 1954, No. 6, 67).

The solvent used was aqueous alcohol (87%). Absorption as well as fluorescence were studied at a concentration of $10^{-4}M$ in neutral, $10^{-4}N$ acidic and $10^{-4}N$ alkaline media. For calculation of integrated absorption (limits 2,100 $\text{\AA}$ and 5,000 $\text{\AA}$) and fluorescence, the areas under the respective spectral curves (on wave-number scale) were measured planimetrically. In comparing fluorescence efficiencies qualitatively, no cognizance has been taken of the spectral distribution of the exciting source.

The compounds used were pure as judged by their melting points.

Thanks are due to Dr. M. G. Marathe for making the compounds available for the present study.